

Improving Kimbundu–Portuguese Neural Machine Translation through Fine-Tuning of Multilingual Models

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Abstract

Neural Machine Translation (NMT) systems have achieved strong performance for high-resource languages; however, many African languages remain underrepresented due to the scarcity of high-quality parallel data. Kimbundu, a Bantu language spoken in Angola, is one such low-resource language with limited machine translation support. In this work, we introduce a manually curated and human-reviewed Kimbundu–Portuguese parallel corpus and investigate its use for fine-tuning multilingual NMT models. By leveraging the NLLB-200 (600M) architecture, we employ parameter-efficient fine-tuning with QLoRA to adapt the model to the Kimbundu→Portuguese direction. Experimental results on a professionally reviewed test set of 1,000 sentence pairs demonstrate substantial improvements over strong multilingual baselines, with gains of +10.1 BLEU and +13.2 chrF. Furthermore, semantic metrics—including COMET, AfriCOMET, and BERTScore—show consistent growth, while qualitative analysis confirms better handling of Kimbundu’s complex morphology. These findings suggest that high-quality human-reviewed data, combined with efficient fine-tuning, is a viable path to bridging the digital divide for low-resource African languages.

1 Introduction

Bantu languages play a central role in everyday communication and cultural preservation across several African countries. Despite their social relevance and large number of speakers, most of these languages remain significantly underrepresented in modern Natural Language Processing (NLP) applications, particularly in machine translation. Although large-scale multilingual models have achieved substantial progress in recent years, their performance remains limited when applied to low-resource languages such as Kimbundu, one of Angola’s national languages.

Figure 1: Most widely spoken mother tongues in Angola in 2024. [Public domain] (of Angola, 2024).

Recent studies have shown that multilingual pre-trained models can improve performance in data-scarce scenarios through cross-lingual knowledge transfer. Nevertheless, persistent challenges remain, mainly due to the limited availability of parallel data and the complex morphological properties of Bantu languages. Previous work, such as (Quinjica and Adelani, 2024), reports improvements in machine translation between Kimbundu and Portuguese, while also highlighting a significant gap in translation quality and linguistic coverage.

Kimbundu is spoken by approximately four million people, making it the third most widely spoken mother tongue in Angola (Figure 1). Despite its historical and sociolinguistic importance, the language has an extremely limited digital presence, primarily due to the lack of annotated corpora and high-quality parallel resources. As a result, machine translation systems and other NLP-based services provide limited or no support for this language.

From a linguistic perspective, Kimbundu follows a canonical subject–verb–object (SVO) word order and exhibits a predominantly agglutinative morphology, in which grammatical categories such as

number and gender are expressed through nominal prefixes. These characteristics differ substantially from those of Indo-European languages that are widely represented in the training data of multilingual models, further exacerbating generalization challenges and negatively impacting machine translation performance.

In this context, this paper investigates how the creation of a carefully constructed and curated parallel dataset can improve the performance of multilingual machine translation models for the Kimbundu–Portuguese language pair. The main contributions of this work are twofold: (i) the introduction of a new human-reviewed parallel dataset for Kimbundu–Portuguese, and (ii) an evaluation of the impact of fine-tuning large-scale multilingual models, comparing them with existing approaches using modern machine translation evaluation metrics. The results demonstrate that appropriate model adaptation strategies can partially mitigate the limitations imposed by data scarcity, reinforcing the potential of transfer learning for low-resource African languages.

2 Related Work

This section reviews initiatives to include the Kimbundu language in natural language processing (NLP) models, as well as studies on other low-resource languages (LRLs). We discuss techniques such as fine-tuning, synthetic data augmentation, and corpus preprocessing.

The work of (Quinjica and Adelani, 2024) addresses the representation of low-resource Angolan languages—Umbundu, Kimbundu, Kikongo, Chokwe, and Luba-Kasai—in multilingual pre-trained language models (PLMs). To mitigate data scarcity, the authors combined synthetic data generated by the NLLB-600M model with the monolingual NLLB corpus, employing the Multilingual Adaptive Fine-tuning (MAFT) approach. They compared models with informed embedding initialization (OFA, ANGOFA) versus random initialization (ANGXLM-R), with ANGOFA achieving the best performance, surpassing the AfroXLMR-base baseline by 12.3 points on the SIB-200 dataset. However, most existing Kimbundu datasets lack proper preprocessing, are small, and have not been reviewed by native speakers or linguistic experts.

Other studies (Adebara et al., 2023; Imani et al., 2023; Team et al., 2022; Kudugunta et al., 2023; Penedo et al., 2025) include Kimbundu in large

multilingual corpora, but often with suboptimal quality due to automated web scraping and reliance on synthetic data. While these works focus on encoder-only models, whereas our study proposes, besides a manually curated dataset, the fine-tuning of an encoder-decoder model for Kimbundu-to-Portuguese machine translation.

Although focused on Kimbundu, challenges such as data scarcity, lack of standardized orthography, and limited digital resources are common across many LRLs. For instance, (Soronnadi et al., 2024) developed IgboBERTa, a RoBERTa-based model trained on a clean Igbo corpus, achieving competitive performance relative to larger models such as XLM-R and AfriBERTa. For Ge’ez, (Wassie, 2024) explored language transfer, token segmentation, and fine-tuning of large models for machine translation, although data scarcity remains a limiting factor.

Other LRL studies include Cantonese (Hong et al., 2024; Dai et al., 2025) and Moroccan Arabic (Darija) (Shang et al., 2024). These works apply data augmentation, back-translation, LoRA fine-tuning, and LLM post-processing to cope with scarce corpora and improve translation quality. Solutions for specific tasks, such as Persian multiple-choice question generation (Zeinalipour et al., 2025) or sentiment analysis in Hausa (Sani et al., 2025), demonstrate the effectiveness of parameter-efficient fine-tuning (PEFT) and language-adaptive fine-tuning (LAFT) methods in low-resource scenarios.

Low-resource automatic speech recognition (ASR) shares similar challenges. Recent studies (Liu et al., 2024; Qian et al., 2024) show that selective fine-tuning, LoRA, and Elastic Weight Consolidation (EWC) improve performance in new languages while preserving pre-existing knowledge, highlighting the applicability of these strategies to low-resource textual tasks.

In summary, existing studies demonstrate advances in dataset quality, multilingual modeling, and parameter-efficient fine-tuning. However, for Kimbundu, limitations remain due to the scarcity of annotated and reviewed data. Our work addresses these gaps by providing a manually curated dataset and fine-tuning a multilingual encoder-decoder model for Kimbundu-to-Portuguese machine translation, offering high-quality, language-specific resources.

3 Construction of the Kimbundu–Portuguese Corpus

3.1 Dataset Creation

Due to the scarcity of digital resources and the absence of a publicly available Kimbundu–Portuguese parallel corpus, it was necessary to manually construct a dataset for machine translation. The corpus was compiled from publicly accessible sources, including religious texts, encyclopedic entries, and educational materials in both languages, as well as notes provided by native Kimbundu speakers that had not been previously digitized.

The collection process aimed to ensure thematic and stylistic diversity, encompassing different types of discourse to enrich the vocabulary and reduce domain bias. All content was selected in accordance with open licensing criteria and for academic use, ensuring that the corpus could be redistributed for research purposes.

3.2 Dataset Pre-processing

The pre-processing pipeline was designed to ensure linguistic quality, structural consistency, and suitability for training machine translation models. Initially, the texts were structured in a *source–target* format, with Kimbundu as the source language and Portuguese as the target language.

To verify that the sentences extracted from online sources were indeed in Kimbundu, the AfroLID classifier (Adebara et al., 2022) was employed for language detection and validation. Although the model produces some false negatives, these cases were manually reviewed to ensure high accuracy in language identification.

To enrich the training set, data augmentation was performed by generating synonyms and semantic paraphrases using large language models, specifically ChatGPT (OpenAI, 2025) and DeepSeek (DeepSeek AI, 2025). The generated sentences were carefully reviewed and validated by a native Kimbundu speaker to preserve the original meaning and linguistic correctness. Data augmentation was applied exclusively to the training set, ensuring that the test set remained free of synthetic content.

The cleaning process included normalization of whitespace, removal of duplicate spaces, and trimming of leading and trailing spaces. Additionally, linguistic noise was removed by filtering out sentences containing HTML or XML tags, URLs, or emojis. Subsequently, exact deduplication based

Metric	Value
Number of sentence pairs	18098
Average source length (tokens)	9.03
Average target length (tokens)	8.74
Maximum source length	218
Maximum target length	299
Vocabulary size (source)	27295
Vocabulary size (target)	27245

Table 1: Statistical summary of the Kimbundu–Portuguese corpus

on sentence equality after normalization was applied to remove redundant pairs, improving both training efficiency and overall data quality, as recommended in the literature (Lee et al., 2022).

After all collection, cleaning, validation, and processing steps, the final corpus consists of 18,098 Kimbundu–Portuguese sentence pairs for training. Additionally, a test set containing 1,000 sentence pairs was constructed by randomly sampling prior to training and carefully evaluated by a professional native Kimbundu speaker, ensuring high-quality references for experimental evaluation.

The statistics presented in Table 1 demonstrate the lexical diversity and sentence length variation within the corpus, characteristics that are important for robust training of machine translation models in low-resource language scenarios.

To ensure transparency and reproducibility, the complete list of sources, as well as the scripts used for collection, cleaning, deduplication, and data splitting, are available in the project’s public repository.¹

4 Fine-tuning

For fine-tuning, we selected the NLLB model (Team et al., 2022), a multilingual machine translation model that includes Kimbundu and other Bantu languages, benefiting from knowledge transfer among typologically related languages. Pre-processing employed the original NLLB tokenizer based on the SentencePiece algorithm, ensuring that subword vocabulary remained consistent with the model embeddings, particularly for Bantu languages including Kimbundu. Moreover, NLLB provides a favorable trade-off between performance and efficiency, as reported in the literature.

Due to computational constraints, we used the NLLB 600M parameter variant and ap-

¹<https://github.com/Ramalheira07/kmbPtMT>

plied Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT) techniques. Specifically, we adopted the Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) method in its quantized QLoRA variant. Training was configured with NF4 quantization and double quantization, using the following hyperparameters: $r = 32$, $\text{lora_alpha} = 64$, $\text{lora_dropout} = 0.05$, and a learning rate of 1.5×10^{-4} . A cosine learning rate scheduler was employed with a warmup ratio of 0.1.

The model was trained for 20 epochs, with a per-device batch size of 16. Training was conducted on a single NVIDIA L4 GPU with 24 GB of memory.

5 Evaluation and Testing

The NLLB (Team et al., 2022) and MADLAD-400 (Kudugunta et al., 2023) models served as the basis for the experimental studies. We evaluated the 600M parameter variant of NLLB and the 3B parameter variant of MADLAD-400. The test set comprises 1,000 Kimbundu–Portuguese sentence pairs.

Based on prior work on machine translation for Bantu languages, multiple automatic metrics were selected to capture different aspects of linguistic quality: BLEU, chrF, chrF++, COMET, BERTScore, and Length Ratio. While BLEU is a traditional metric, its effectiveness in low-resource and morphologically rich languages is limited, as its word-level n-gram counts are sensitive to tokenization and morphological variation.

In contrast, chrF measures n-gram character-level precision and recall, making it more robust for languages with complex morphology (Popović, 2015). Its extension, chrF++, complements this approach by including word n-grams (Popovic, 2017), exhibiting higher correlation with human judgments. For deeper evaluation, COMET (Rei et al., 2020) and its specialized variant AfriCOMET were employed; these use multilingual neural language models to project the source, translation, and reference sentences into a shared vector space. Finally, BERTScore (Zhang et al., 2020) was applied to assess semantic similarity through contextualized embeddings, focusing on meaning rather than surface-level term matching.

6 Results

In this section, we present the results of the training and fine-tuning of the base NLLB model, as well as the experimental evaluation of the machine translation systems for the Kimbundu \rightarrow Portuguese

language pair. For the evaluation, we exclusively used a manually curated test set, deliberately avoiding synthetic data in this study; the impact of synthetic data will be explored in future work. Reference (*baseline*) models, namely NLLB-600M and MADLAD-400 3B, were compared with the fine-tuned NLLB model. Quantitative evaluation was performed using the chrF, chrF++, BLEU (with appropriate caveats regarding its suitability for low-resource languages), COMET, and AfriCOMET metrics.

The training and fine-tuning results of the 600M-parameter multilingual NLLB model show stable behavior throughout the optimization process. Training begins to converge around the 12th epoch, after which only marginal improvements are observed until the end of the run. Figures 2 and 3 show the evolution of the *training loss* and *validation loss*, respectively. Additionally, Figure 4 illustrates the relationship between training loss and the chrF metric during fine-tuning, highlighting the correlation between loss reduction and improved translation quality.

Finally, Table 2 presents the quantitative results obtained by the evaluated models, complemented by two qualitative translation examples. These examples include a longer narrative sentence as well as a short sentence with minimal context, allowing for analysis of model behavior across different linguistic scenarios.

Figure 2: Training loss during fine-tuning. Line plot showing the decrease of training loss over 9600 steps, from approximately 2.28 to 1.69.

Example 1 Source text (Kimbundu):

Diyala anga usanga bhwama, bhwala kiditadi kyonene, kyala ni dibhitu. Mwene ubokola moxi a ditadi. O muhutu k'a mu mwenye dingi. Anga uvutuka kwoso kwatundu, anga uya ku bhata dya manyi

Model	BLEU	chrF	chrF++	COMET	AfriCOMET	BERTScore	Len. Ratio
MADLAD T5 (3B)	1.95	15.14	13.91	.4672	.2998	.6828	1.72
NLLB-600M Base	7.70	25.64	24.08	.6179	.4550	.7674	1.02
NLLB Fine-tuned	17.85	38.87	37.65	.6702	.5169	.8161	.97

Table 2: Results of the automated evaluation of the translation models.

Figure 3: Validation loss during fine-tuning. Line plot showing the decrease of validation loss over 9600 steps, from approximately 2.09 to 1.79.

Figure 4: Relationship between training loss and chrF during fine-tuning (dual-axis). Dual-axis line plot showing training loss decreasing from 2.28 to 1.69 and chrF increasing from 35.1 to 41.1 over 9600 training steps.

ya.

Reference (Portuguese):

O homem então encontra um lugar onde há uma grande rocha, que tem uma porta. Ele entra dentro da rocha. A mulher não o viu novamente. E ela voltou de onde veio e foi para a casa de sua mãe.

MADLAD T5 (3B):

E disse-lhes: Se alguém vos pedir um pão, trazei-o, e comei-o; se alguém vos pedir um vinho, bebei-o; se alguém vos pedir um vinho, bebei-o; se alguém vos pedir um vinho, bebei-o; se alguém vos

pedir um vinho, bebei-o; se alguém vos pedir um vinho, bebei-o.

NLLB-600M Base:

Quando a mulher chegou, viu que havia uma pedra aberta, e a porta estava aberta, e ele roubou-a dentro de uma pedra, e a mulher não o deixou entrar, e voltou para a casa do homem.

NLLB Fine-tuned:

O homem encontra lá uma grande pedra com porta. Ele bate debaixo da pedra. A mulher não a encontra mais. Então, ele volta de onde saiu e vai para a casa da mulher.

7 Discussion

The results presented in Table 2 highlight substantial performance differences among the evaluated models, both in n-gram-based metrics and semantic metrics. Overall, it is observed that the *NLLB Fine-tuned* model consistently outperforms the other approaches across all considered metrics, indicating that fine-tuning with language-specific data and human review is crucial for improving translation quality in low-resource scenarios.

The MADLAD T5 (3B) model, despite its high parametric capacity and large-scale training on multilingual and documentary data, exhibits significantly lower performance. This outcome suggests that generalist foundation models, when applied directly (*zero-shot*) to underrepresented languages, may not adequately capture specific linguistic phenomena such as morphological variations, particular syntactic structures, and semantic patterns inherent to Bantu languages.

In contrast, the NLLB-600M Base model demonstrates intermediate performance, clearly surpassing MADLAD T5 across all metrics. This behavior can be attributed to NLLB’s explicit focus on low-resource language coverage during pretraining. However, the substantial difference between

Category	Content	Note/Error
Source Reference	Phange yami (Phange yami ya diyala) Meu irmão	Original (Kimbundu) Human Translation
MADLAD T5	Phange yami (Phange yami ya ttiya)	Overgeneration
NLLB Base	Meu irmão (meu primo)	Semantic error
NLLB FT	Meu irmão (meu irmão)	Correct Translation

Table 3: Comparison of translation outputs.

the NLLB Base and the NLLB Fine-tuned model indicates that pretraining, while essential, is insufficient to achieve high translation quality without adaptation to the specific domain and target language.

Semantic metrics, namely COMET, AfriCOMET, and BERTScore, further support this analysis by showing consistent gains after fine-tuning. In particular, AfriCOMET, designed for African contexts and underrepresented languages, is sensitive to improvements introduced by fine-tuning, confirming its suitability for more faithful evaluations of semantic quality in Bantu languages.

The *length ratio* analysis also reveals notable differences in model behavior. The high value observed for MADLAD T5 indicates a tendency toward over-generation, possibly related to difficulties in controlling translation fluency and length appropriateness. Conversely, the values close to 1 observed for the NLLB models suggest greater stability in generation, with the fine-tuned model achieving the best balance between conciseness and informational coverage.

Examples further highlight significant limitations of MADLAD T5 in *zero-shot* scenarios, including extreme over-generation and complete loss of semantic alignment (Example 1). Additionally, MADLAD exhibits a pronounced bias deviation when handling religious content, often amplifying or distorting theological terms beyond the source meaning. The NLLB Base model demonstrates better structural adequacy, though it still produces semantic errors and incorrect inferences. In contrast, the NLLB Fine-tuned model produces translations closer to the reference, preserving meaning and demonstrating better lexical control, even in short and semantically sensitive sentences (Table 3).

Overall, the results demonstrate that, for low-resource languages, supervised adaptation strategies remain crucial, even in the era of large foundation models. These findings reinforce the im-

portance of investing in high-quality parallel data curation and creating specific fine-tuning pipelines, particularly for African languages historically neglected in machine translation scenarios.

8 Conclusion

In this work, we analyzed the presence and degree of inclusion of the low-resource Kimbundu language in major multilingual machine translation models. The construction of a Kimbundu dataset with human review, combined with the application of efficient parameter fine-tuning techniques on multilingual models, proved to be a promising approach to mitigate the challenges faced by low-resource languages. This strategy enables such languages to more effectively benefit from knowledge transfer, particularly when there is morphological and typological proximity with other languages present in the model training.

Based on theoretical studies and experimental tests, we conclude that the multilingual model best suited for translating Kimbundu is NLLB. This superior performance can be attributed to its ability to efficiently model the internal structures of Bantu languages, as reflected in its architecture and the data used during training, making it particularly suitable for translation scenarios involving low-resource African languages.

Limitations

This work has several limitations. First, we did not explore large-scale synthetic data generation strategies such as back-translation or fully automatic corpus expansion, which constrained the size of the training set. The only form of data augmentation applied consisted of the generation of synonyms and semantic paraphrases, which were manually reviewed and validated by a native Kimbundu speaker to preserve meaning and linguistic correctness. These constraints were primarily due to the low-resource setting and the available computational infrastructure, which also limited the scale

of the models used.

Second, our study focused exclusively on textual data, leaving the exploration of speech-based resources, such as automatic speech recognition (ASR), for the low-resource Kimbundu language as an avenue for future work.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the use of AI-based language models (ChatGPT by OpenAI) to assist in the organization, linguistic refinement, and clarity improvement of the manuscript. The authors also thank two professionals, native speakers of Kimbundu, for their invaluable assistance in inspecting and validating the datasets. All scientific content, interpretations, and conclusions remain the sole responsibility of the authors.

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